

Item	ONBOARDING: Your responsibility as a new team member	Link	OFFBOARDING: Your responsibility as an alumnus
Initiate Process	Please make sure your PI sends an email to our Project Manager, Laurel Cooper, to introduce you. Laurel will share the Google Drive with you so you can get started.	https://bit.ly/gpe-docs	Review with your PI which aspects of the project you will need to access after you leave and for how long.
Overlap	If you are replacing someone, please ensure transfer of knowledge has been completed and learn as much as you can from them before they leave.	N/A	If someone is replacing you, speak to them as much as you can before you leave. Make sure they know how to get onboarded.
Contact Information	Fill out the Team spreadsheet with your information. Give the project manager 24 hours to add you to the calendar, slack, etc. Be sure to check the "current" box.		Do not delete any information. Only uncheck the "current" box
GenoPhenoEnvo Governance	Study the GenoPhenoEnvo Governance, and let Anne know whether you have any comments, suggestions, or questions. When ready, send a written note to let her and the team know that you approve and agree with its contents.	https://bit.ly/gpe-gom	No action needed.
Orientation	Review the project summary slides		
Internal Meetings Agenda & Notes	To become more acquainted with the latest work, please read over this document.	GenoPhenoEnvo Internal Meeting: Agenda and Notes .	No action needed.
Calendar	Make sure you have access to the project calendar and ask to be added if not.	GenoPhenoEnvo Project Calendar	Ask to be removed from the calendar.
GenoPhenoEnvo Mailing Lists	Email Laurel with your primary email address (for subscription with 'all notifications'). If different from the primary one, provide also your Gmail address (for subscription with 'no notifications').	Public: https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/genophenoenvo Internal: https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/genophenoenvo-internal	Unsubscribe from the Mailing Lists
GitHub	Make sure you have access to the GenoPhenoEnvo GitHub organization and ask to be added if not. Need to create a GitHub ID, if you do not have one. Please set your membership in the GenoPhenoEnvo Organization to 'Public.' You can either do this when you first confirm that you are joining the organization, or by finding your entry in the list of 'People' that belong to the organization.	https://github.com/genophenoenvo	Email Laurel/ Anne to request being removed from the GitHub Org.
Slack	Make sure you have access to the GenoPhenoEnvo work space on Slack and ask to be added if not.	GenoPhenoEnvo Slack Workspace	Please leave the GenoPhenoEnvo work space on Slack
Roles & Responsibilities	Add yourself to the Roles & Responsibilities table in GitHub	https://github.com/genophenoenvo/team_members	Remove yourself from the Roles & Responsibilities table in GitHub
Org Chart			
Other projects	If required, onboard to related projects.	Ask the team for links to other projects	Offboard from related projects, if required